

SUPPORT TO MODULAR LEARNING MODALITY AND STUDENTS' ACHIEVEMENT IN TLE 7: BASIS FOR CURRICULUM INNOVATION

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ABSTRACT

This study was undertaken to determine the perceived support to modular distance learning modality and student's achievement in TLE 7 as basis for curriculum innovation. The descriptive method of research was utilized in this study with the use of survey questionnaire in google form checklist using a Likert scale participated by one hundred twenty one (121) respondents. The statistical tool used to interpret the gathered data were mean, frequency, percentage and standard deviation. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was also used to find out if there is a significant relationship between independent variables which consists of support to modular distance learning modality in terms of personal, family, school, and community and the dependent variables that includes the students' achievement in TLE 7 for the 1st quarter and 2nd quarter. Based on the findings, majority of the respondents perceived that personal, family, school, and community support were highly evident having an overall mean of 3.46 and SD of 0.478. The written work of the students were almost the same in the 1st and 2nd quarters having a rating mean of 80.47 and 80.57 respectively. The same with the performance task mean rating with 82.79 and 82.58 respectively. This research study concluded that the hypothesis stating that the profile of the respondents has no significant relationship to the students' achievement in TLE 7 is therefore accepted. Similarly, the hypothesis stating that the perceived support to modular distance learning modality has no significant relationship to the students' achievement in TLE 7 is also accepted.

Keywords: modular distance learning modality, curriculum innovation, Likert scale, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient